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Atomic force microscopy and nanoindentation of cement pastes with nanotube dispersions

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Since their discovery in 1991 by Iijima [1], carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have probably become the most promising nanomaterials due to their unique mechanical, electronic and chemical properties. Our aim is to improve the mechanical properties of cement pastes by the addition of CNTs, giving rise to a new and higher-performance composite material. To reach an efficient cement-based composite with nanotubes we have studied the addition of different CNT concentrations in the mix design in order to obtain enhanced mechanical properties with respect to plain cement pastes. We have measured the micro-hardness and Young's modulus of the composites by nanoindenting with a sharp diamond three-sided pyramidal tip mounted on an Atomic Force Microscope probe. These measurements have been correlated with the average macroscopic Young's modulus.

1 Introduction

This paper presents a research study on the mechanical properties of cement-based composites reinforced with carbon nanotubes. It is restricted to the reinforcement of the cement paste matrix as a first step to a further study of more complex materials.

The cement paste matrix is in itself a multi-phase material. Basically, it is a porous material composed of calcium hydroxide (portlandite), aluminates and unhydrated clinker embedded into an amorphous nanostructured hydration product, the so-called C-S-H gel [2]. The C-S-H gel is the most important hydration product of cement (50–70% of the hydration product by volume) with a characteristic length scale ranging from 1 nm to 100 nm. C-S-H accounts for “calcium silicate hydrate” with a variable composition which is the reason for the hyphenated notation. Two different phases of C-S-H gel have been identified [3, 4], a low density C-S-H (LD C-S-H), formed during the first stages of the hydration, and a high density C-S-H (HD C-S-H) which is formed as the hydration process goes further. By performing nanoindentation experiments, the mechanical properties and proportion of the two C-S-H gel species have been reported [4].

Carbon nanotube discovery is attributed to Iijima in 1991 [1]. Carbon nanotubes are synthesized on two distinct morphologies [5], single-walled nanotubes (SWNT) which are composed of only one Graphene sheet rolled into a cylinder (Fig. 1) and multi-walled nanotubes (MWNT) which consist of multiple concentric graphene cylinders. These graphene cylinders have diameters on the order of nanometers and lengths of microns. They are believed to be the future substitutes for carbon fibres because of their outstanding properties [5]. Carbon nanotubes are stronger than steel, but lightweight and can bear torsion and bending without breaking [6, 7]. Theoretical calculations predict a Young's modulus between 1 to 5 TPa for single walled nanotubes [8–10] which means that carbon nanotubes can have a tensile strength higher than any carbon fibre known (high modulus carbon fibre have a Young's modulus of about 400 GPa). Furthermore, carbon nanotubes also present extraordinary thermal and electrical properties: they are thermally stable until 2800 °C in vacuum, their thermal conductivity is about two times that of diamond and their electrical conductivity is about 1000 times the conductivity of copper [11]. In addition, depending upon diameter and helicity, they can be conductors or semiconductors [5].

However, due to the interaction between the graphene sheets of the nanotubes, these tubes aggregate to form bundles or “ropes” that are very difficult to disperse. In the case of singlewalled nanotubes, the bundles consist of many nanotubes, and have diameters ranging from 10 to 200 nm. Ropes are even entangled with one another. Therefore, they must be disentangled, although it is extremely difficult to achieve a uniform dispersion at the single tube level, above all in aqueous media such as that for cement composites. Furthermore, due to their graphitic nature, there is not a proper adhesion between the nanotube and the matrix causing what it is called sliding. Since nanotubes are assembled in bundles, there is an additional sliding inside the bundle. Both the non homogeneous dispersion of the nanotubes and the lack of interaction with the matrix prevent nanotubes from exhibiting their outstanding mechanical properties in nanocomposites. Proper dispersion and adequate load transfer are the main challenges in the search for efficient carbon nanotube reinforced composites.

First attempts to produce carbon nanotube reinforced cementitious composites have been recently reported [12–14]. In Ref. [13] the average compressive strength was discussed for reinforced cement paste matrices with SWNTs and MWNTs, and In Ref. [12] the electromagnetic shielding effectiveness was reported for millimetre waves. In the present work a nanoindentation study to measure the Young's modulus and hardness of the carbon nanotube reinforced cement paste matrices is presented.

2 Experimental

The pastes used for the study were made from cem I 52.5 R. This type of cement has been selected because it presents the finest granulometry of all the commercial cements which suits best for the inclusion of nanomaterials. As shown in Table 1 a reference sample (C0) was first prepared in order to study the impact of the addition of the nanotubes. The carbon nanotubes used in the dispersions were commercially acquired from Shenzhen Nanotech Port Co. (NTP). In the case of SWNTs, they have a purity of more than 90%, diameter less than 2 nm and length less than 20 μm , and MWNTs have a purity of more than 90%, diameter of 10 to 20 nm and lengths from 1 to 50 μm .

Both single and multi walled carbon nanotubes were dispersed in the mix. The nanotube dispersions were carried out in plain distilled water (CM1, CM2, CS1 and CS2) and in water with gum arabic powder (CGM1 and CGS1) to improve the dispersion of the nanotubes as demonstrated in Ref. [15, 16]. After mixing, different amounts were moulded into prism-shaped specimens ($1 \times 1 \times 6 \text{ cm}^3$) and compacted by vibration. The specimens were demoulded after 1 day at >90% relative humidity. Subsequently groups of six specimens for each mix were stored at the temperature of $21 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under water for 28 days.

After 28 days, flexural and compressive strength were measured. For the nanoindentation measurements, a little piece of sample was cut, embedded in epoxy resin and polished. The samples were visualised firstly with the AFM and then the nanoindentation experiments were performed, see Fig. 2.

These samples were scanned with a Digital Instruments Nanoscope III Dimension 3100 atomic force microscope. The atomic force microscope (AFM) was invented in 1986 [17], and since then, it has been possible to measure local properties of many kinds of materials with a spatial resolution of nanometers using a sharp tip for scanning over (at a distance of nanometres) a solid surface. With this type of microscope the surface topography can be characterized, as well as the mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of samples, with the appropriate probes. In our experiment, tapping-mode AFM imaging was used to characterize the surface structures of the polished CNT/Cement composites. The samples are embedded into an epoxy resin, ground and polished with different diamond dispersions up to a grain size of 1 μm , as AFM imaging requires a substantially flat surface.

The mechanical properties of the samples were measured using the nanoindentation module of the AFM. In a nanoindentation experiment, the AFM tip is positioned over a flat region of the surface. Then the tip is lowered to indent the surface up to a specified load, and then raised again while the system records all the data of load, deflection and position. There are advantages and disadvantages in using AFM for nanoindentation instead of typical nanoindenters. The main disadvantage of using an AFM for nanoindentation is that it is difficult to get a proper calibration measurement and, therefore, the data taken by an AFM will be more qualitative than in the case of a typical nanoindenter where calibration is straightforward. The advantage of the AFM over a nanoindenter is that it allows lower loads, and a better positioning accuracy. Another important difference is that forces are inferred from the measured deflection of the cantilever in the case of the AFM, whereas a typical nanoindenter performs force controlled measurements.

The elastic modulus can be evaluated, based on the measured parameters, by using the approach of Sneddon [18, 19]. This method utilizes the relationship between load and penetration depth as explained in the next section.

3 Theory

A schematic figure of indentation load, P , versus displacement data, h , obtained during one indentation is presented in Fig. 3. The relevant parameters are the maximum load, P_{max} , the maximum depth, h_{max} , and the slope of the upper part of the unloading curve, $S = dP/dh$. These parameters are then used to calculate the

hardness and the Young's modulus, $H=P_{max}/A$ and $E_r = \sqrt{\pi} \cdot S/2\sqrt{A}$, where A is the projected contact area at the load P , and E_r is the reduced Young's modulus which is used because the elastic displacements occur in both the indenter and the sample. The Young's modulus of the sample, E , is derived from E_r by:

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E_r} + \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i}$$

Where ν is the Poisson's ratio for the sample, and E_i and ν_i are the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the indenter respectively. However, in order to calculate the Hardness and Young's modulus of the samples, the projected contact area has to be estimated. In the case of a three-sided pyramidal tip, this area is $A = 3\sqrt{3}h_p^2 \tan^2 \alpha$, where α is the angle of the tip, which is 21.6° in our case. h_p is calculated from the measured h_{max} and the slope of the unloading curve, $h_{max}=h_p+h_a$, and the parameter h_a is calculated as follows:

$$h_a = \left\{ \frac{(\pi - 2) \cdot 2}{\pi} \right\} \frac{P_{max}}{dP/dh}$$

where dP/dh is the slope of the unloading curve at the maximum load.

4 Results and discussion

The Young's modulus and the hardness were calculated from the data obtained in the experiments and were plotted versus their frequency of appearance in order to obtain their corresponding distributions. In Fig. 4 both distributions for the plain cement paste (C0) are shown. Our results are in good agreement with those reported in Ref. [4] for the values of the Young modulus (between 20 and 30 GPa). Our two C–S–H gel phases are distributed 80% for the LD C–S–H and 20% for the HD C–S–H respectively, whereas the distribution reported in Ref. [4] is 70% and 30% for the LD C–S–H and HD C–S–H respectively. The differences could come from the different w/c ratio employed in each experiment. In our case the w/c ratio was 0.34 which maybe was insufficient to reach full hydration of the HD C–S–H phase since this is the phase that forms at a later stage, while it was 0.5 in Ref. [4] allowing for full hydration of both phases.

In Table 2 the peaks and percentages of the two phases of C–S–H for the Young's modulus and Hardness distributions are presented for all the cases under study.

The plain cement paste (C0) will be taken as a reference to study the impact of the addition of the carbon nanotubes in the different samples. Overall, the samples containing nanotubes but without gum arabic (CM1, CM2, CS1 and CS2) have worse mechanical properties than the plain cement paste. This behaviour stems from the afore-mentioned difficulties in the dispersion of the nanotubes in aqueous media due to their intrinsic hydrophobicity. This leads to a non-uniform distribution of the bundles within the matrix which provokes a decrease in the mechanical properties. This behaviour is even more marked in our case because our SWNTs are straighter and more defect-free structures than our MWNTs, so that it is more difficult to disperse the SWNTs and to get a minimum interaction with the matrix. Therefore, the samples containing MWNTs show a higher Young's modulus and hardness than the ones with SWNTs. Another result that supports this discussion is the fact that the samples with lower concentration of nanotubes get better mechanical properties in both cases (with SWNTs and MWNTs). Furthermore, it has been shown [12] that the nanotube incorporation in cement pastes without any dispersing agent affects the cement hydration process. Therefore, as the nanotube quantity in the mix is increased a worse dispersion is obtained (more agglomeration and less uniform distribution throughout the matrix) and the hydration of cement is decreased, thus impairing the mechanical performance.

In the case of the samples with the nanotubes pre-dispersed with gum arabic (CGM1 and CGS1), a different trend is observed: both the Young's modulus and the hardness increase with respect to the same samples without the gum arabic (CM1 and CS1), although the distribution of these properties is shifted towards the LD C–S–H value. The sample with SWNTs (CGS1) shows a considerable enhancement of the mechanical properties, whereas the enhancement is not so high for the MWNTs. As demonstrated in Ref. [15] gum Arabic is a powerful dispersing agent for carbon nanotubes and it also has the advantage of being compatible with cement-based materials [12, 20] within a reasonable limit of addition. Therefore it can disperse the nanotubes without impairing the cement hydration such as usual nanotube dispersing agents do (for example SDS, Triton X100, toluene, ethanol, etc.). The higher change in the samples with SWNTs

can be understood as a result of the superior properties of SWNTs when properly dispersed and of the lower quantity of SWNTs and gum arabic in the mix, indicating that the mix design is closer to an optimum value. This fact must be further investigated.

5 Conclusions

We have presented preliminary results on the modification of cement pastes by the addition of carbon nanotubes. The impact of both SWNTs and MWNTs on the Young's modulus and hardness has been analysed by performing nanoindentation measurements.

Both MWNTs and SWNTs have been added to cement paste without any dispersing agent and as a pre-mix of the carbon nanotubes and the mixing water with gum arabic. Overall, the samples containing nanotubes but without gum arabic have shown worse mechanical properties than the plain cement paste due to the intrinsic hydrophobicity of the nanotubes and their impact on the hydration process. However when pre-dispersing the nanotubes with gum arabic an increase in the mechanical properties is achieved, above all in the case of SWNTs. It is suggested that studies should be aimed at establishing the optimum values of carbon nanotubes and dispersing agents in the mix design parameters. Research in this direction is now under progress.

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Table 1 Composition of the different composite materials.

	C0	CGM1	CGS1	CM1	CM2	CS1	CS2
water/cement	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34
gum arabic (wt%)	-	2.00%	1.00%	-	-	-	-
MWNT	-	0.20%	-	0.20%	0.10%	-	-
SWNT	-	-	0.10%	-	-	0.10%	0.05%

Table 2 Young's modulus and Hardness distributions of the samples under study.

	E_{LD} (GPa)	E_{HD} (GPa)	H_{LD} (GPa)	H_{HD} (GPa)
C0	23.0 (80%)	33.0 (20%)	13.0 (76%)	22.0 (24%)
CGM1	17.5 (84%)	36.0 (16%)	3.6 (86%)	9.1 (14%)
CGS1	23.0 (87%)	58.0 (13%)	6.0 (90%)	15.0 (10%)
CM1	15.0 (87%)	33.5 (13%)	3.5 (82%)	7.5 (18%)
CM2	31.0 (76%)	75.0 (24%)	4.0 (76%)	12.5 (24%)
CS1	6.5 (90%)	11.0 (10%)	2.0 (90%)	4.5 (10%)
CS2	7.0 (83%)	14.5 (17%)	3.0 (90%)	9.5 (10%)

Fig. 1 Carbon nanotube rolling from a grapheme sheet.

Fig. 2 (online colour at: www.pss-a.com) AFM scanning over cement paste, a) 2D image before nanoindentation, b) after nanoindentation and c) 3D topographic image.

Fig. 3 Schematic figure of indentation load vs. displacement data during one indentation.

Fig. 4 Sample C0, cement powder with distilled water, a) Young's modulus, b) Hardness.

